
A socio-pragmatic study of the language of instruction in science classrooms: Insights from speech acts theory

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Abstract: Speech acts are performed in classroom discourse, which reveals the intention of teachers about the topics that the students are taught. Also, the language of instruction used to convey these speech acts is pivotal in ensuring a high or appreciable level of mastery of the topics of discussion by the students. This study examined various illocutionary acts used in classroom interactions and assessed the language of instruction used in senior secondary II (SS 2) science classrooms in selected secondary schools in Osun State. The primary data is drawn from the analysis of classroom recordings from six classroom interactions of Senior Secondary School II (SS 2) science classes during Mathematics, Biology, and Physics classes. 6 secondary schools were randomly selected in six local government areas of Osun State. The result showed that eight illocutionary acts were used during the six classroom interactions, including expressive, directive, interrogative, affirmative, denial, vocative, corrective, and commissive, in which expressive was the main illocutionary act used in the classroom interactions. Also, three languages of instruction were used in the classroom interactions, which included English only, Yoruba only, and bilingual instruction. However, English speech acts were mainly used in all the classroom interactions, and sometimes, the bilingual speech acts were also used. It is recommended that English should be complemented with the child's mother tongue because the use of the bilingual medium of instruction will enhance better understanding and performance of the students in their subjects in ESL classrooms.

Keywords: Bilingual, Classrooms, English, Language of instruction, Speech Acts

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Mrs Mercy Mary Akinbosoye is an emerging scholar with a passion for the social and stylistic aspects of language usage. With almost a decade of experience in the teaching of the English language in secondary schools. Mercy has hands-on experience in the intricacies of the language. Currently, Mercy stands at the threshold of academia as she recently embarked on her scholastic journey to her doctorate degree in the University of Ibadan. Mercy aims at bridging the gap between linguistic theories and social realities.

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1. Introduction

It is impossible to overlook the importance of language in education since it is the means by which teachers impart knowledge and instruction to students, and learning cannot be accomplished without language. According to Amadi (2012), language is the fundamental instrument for gaining knowledge, which is extremely important for learning because learning is linked to meaning. When communicating, a person reacts to the semantic significance of the words spoken rather than merely the sounds. In classroom discourse, some illocutionary acts are performed by the teachers and the students in order to be able to convey the intentions of both participants so that there can be an engaging and educative classroom interaction. Also, the language of instruction used in classroom interactions is pivotal to enhance a high or appreciable level of mastery of the topics of discussion. This is why this study intends to examine various illocutionary acts used in classroom interactions and assess the language of instruction used in senior secondary II (SS 2) science classrooms in selected secondary schools in Osun State.

2. Literature review

2.1. Conditions for Effective Classroom Communication

Language is an important tool of communication that human beings use to interact and communicate in society, and anybody without language access cannot lead a normal life and cannot attain self-actualization (Oso, 2025). Communication is made possible by language proficiency, which necessitates having a solid command of speaking, listening, reading, and writing (Mahendran et al., 2026). According to Habaci et al. (2013), in educational communication processes, the instructor is the source and the student is the recipient. The message can be found in the curriculum, the coursebook, or the instructor's voice. The instructional methods or resources are the channel. According to Habaci (2013), the primary goal of good communication in the classroom is to provide an atmosphere that facilitates the efficient exchange of messages between students and teachers. Beyond the idea that "teacher speaks and students listen" (Woolfolk, 1995 in Silman, 2007), communication should be two-way. One-way communication should not be encouraged in the classroom since communication is the complex exchange of knowledge. It is important for students to communicate with one another as well as with their teachers (Balay, 2009). This means that for information to be transferred effectively and efficiently, all parties must encode and decode messages in an understandable manner.

Effective communication requires both teachers and students to be proficient in the language they are using. This reveals the importance of using an appropriate language of instruction in classroom discussion. According to Olagbaju and Akinsowon (2014), it is crucial to employ "appropriate" language in education, which is defined as a language that can successfully convey to the student all of the teacher's goals in a way that the student can comprehend. The language of instruction that should be used should be the one that is appropriate for both teachers and students.

2.2. Overview of types of language of instruction

Language has a crucial role in education, according to Oso (2024a), and as a result, a language or combination of languages serves as the medium of instruction at various formal education levels. The mother tongue medium of instruction, the transitional-bilingual medium of instruction, the bilingual-biliterate (codemixing) medium of instruction, and the English medium of instruction are among the various forms of media of instruction that can be employed in the formal education system (Oso, 2024a). The mother-tongue medium of instruction is the sole use of the mother tongue for teaching in the classroom. According to research by Oribabor and Adesina (2013), Chisunum and Ejie (2014), Ojetunde (2012) and Asiyanbola and Ademilokun (2015), this medium is the best for the primary school pupils. Another is the transitional bilingual medium of instruction, which is the medium of instruction stated in the National Policy on Education (2013) that should be used in the primary schools, whereby the mother tongue is used at the first three years of the primary school education, while English language is used at the last three years of primary education. This is referred to as "three-tier instruction" by Dutcher and Tucker (1997), which suggests that the child starts primary school in his mother tongue, rapidly learns a lingua franca or regional language, and then advances to the language of wider communication.

Furthermore, the bilingual-biliterate medium of instruction (codemixing) is when the mother tongue and English complement one another in the delivery of education in schools (Oso, 2024a). It occurs when the teacher teaches in one language and simultaneously translates the same in a second language (Amadi 2012). This is usually practiced in Nigerian schools. According to Amao (2010), Amadi (2012), and Oso (2024a), bilingual education greatly enhances students' academic performance by ensuring that complex vocabulary, registers, and concepts are thoroughly comprehended. This is due to the fact that learning would be improved if the teacher used simultaneous translation in both the mother tongue and the second language during his teaching process. Additionally, when English is the only language utilized for instruction in schools, this is referred to as the English medium of instruction. However, Oso (2024a) found that the use of English as the only medium of instruction is no longer practiced because teachers try their best to teach the students in both English and Yoruba, the mother tongue of the majority of the students, in order to ensure an effective dissemination of information and knowledge and ultimately achieve the goal of teaching the students in the first place.

2.3. Speech Act Theory by J.R. Searle

Speech act theory cannot be discussed without making reference to J.L. Austin. This is because this theory was introduced by him and further developed by the American philosopher J.R. Searle. According to Austin (1962), Speech Act Theory describes and classifies the different kinds of things people do when they use sentences in an actual speech. Language is not only used in saying things but also in performing actions. The basic emphasis of Speech Act Theory is what an utterer means by the utterances spoken. In this study, Speech Act Theory comes into play by looking at instances of English

speech acts, Yoruba speech acts, and bilingual speech acts. The English speech acts refer to statements that are uttered in the English language in classroom interactions, Yoruba speech acts refer to statements that are uttered in the Yoruba language in classroom interactions, while the bilingual speech acts are the statements that are uttered by code-mixing English and Yoruba in classroom interactions.

Austin divides the linguistic act into three components. We have the locutionary act, illocutionary act, and perlocutionary act. The locutionary act is the act of saying something with a certain meaning; the illocutionary act is when the intention of the speaker is expressed to the hearer through the use of language, while the perlocutionary act is the effect an utterance has on the hearer, which can serve as a warning, a request, persuasion, undertaking, informing, apology, and many more. Though there are three components of speech acts, this study is concerned with illocutionary acts because the concept of illocutionary acts is central to the concept of Speech Act Theory. For Searle, the basic unit of language is the illocutionary act. Searle (1976) further identified five illocutionary acts, which include representatives or assertive, commissive, expressive, declarations, and directives.

- i.) **Representatives or Assertive:** These are statements that describe the state of affairs of things and situations in the world. This involves asserting, concluding, informing, reporting, predicting, e.g. *It is going to rain tonight.*
- ii.) **Directives:** These are statements that try to make the hearer or addressee perform an action. These include asking, begging, ordering, mandating, advising, inviting, interrogating, e.g. *Come back here, Can you open the door?*
- iii.) **Commissive:** These are statements that commit the speaker to doing something in the future. These include promising, vowing, betting, opposing, threatening, guaranteeing, e.g. *I will come tomorrow., I must deal with him.*
- iv.) **Expressive:** These are statements that express how the speaker feels about the situation. These include thanking, welcoming, deploring, apologizing, blaming, rebuking, complaining, greeting, e.g. *This meal is delicious., Don't be angry with me.*
- v.) **Declaratives:** These are statements that change the state of the world in an immediate way. These include declaring war, pronouncing husband and wife, performing a marriage, pronouncing someone guilty, baptizing, for example. *I pronounce you husband and wife., You are hereby sentenced to death by hanging., You are fired., Objection overruled.* (pp.10-14).

There have been some modifications of Searle's (1976) Speech acts theory. Searle's ideas serve as the foundation for Katz's (2015) taxonomy of speech acts, which she feels is more internally consistent than Searle's own. She separated the speech act classes according to their expressed psychological states and potential propositional content, and she defined additional subcategories according to the illocutionary force and facial affects that each category's members could express.

1. **Descriptives:** Word-to-world is the direction of fit for this class of speech acts. These statements convey the speakers' psychological states because they think their propositional content is true. Subjective and objective descriptives are the two categories into which they are separated. Both objective and subjective descriptives' primary illocutionary goal is to present descriptive information.
2. Objective descriptives give a description of the speaker's surroundings or environment. It can also be used as positive impoliteness to attack the addressee's face. For example, *steady-state micro-welding always produces more smoke than fire., Nigeria is rich in oil and gas.*
3. Subjective descriptives describe the speaker's mental state. It is employed to enhance the good face of the addressee and lessen that of the speaker. For example, *I said I don't want to go out today., I am sorry I ruined your outfit.* (Katz, 2015: 51-52).
4. **Obligative:** The world-to-word fit of this speech act is more expansive than word-to-world class. It conveys the wish for someone to carry out a certain action in the future. Obligative fall into two categories: persuasives and commissive. Numerous techniques for politeness and impoliteness can be used in both persuasive and commissive.
5. **Commissive:** This conveys the speaker's desired activities. The main face effect of commissive is to lessen the speaker's unfavorable face. For example, *would you be kind enough to follow me to see her?* For example, *I would like to remind you of what you promised me.*
6. **Persuasives:** This states what the addressee is expected to do. The main effect of persuasives is to make the addressee appear less negative. Example: *Would you be kind enough to follow me to see her?* (Katz, 2015: 52).
7. **Performatives:** Performatives resemble Searle's class of declarations and Austin's class of verdictives. They are statements that, by virtue of their utterance, change the world to suit their content, without requiring a person to take any action. The speaker's psychological condition is characterized by their urge to make an instant environmental change. (Katz 2015: 53). Performatives, such as a person's christening, a court decision, or the marriage of two individuals, are highly context-dependent and require a speaker who has been granted the authority by society to bring about these changes (Austin, 1975). Some, like betting or bequeathing, simply need a specific context.

Asiyanbola (2009) in his paper expounded the illocutionary acts used by former President Obasanjo's 46th Nigerian Independence speech to 11 illocutionary acts which include assertive, informing, confirming, judging, promising, denying, requesting, greeting, questioning, condemning and regretting in order to cater for the different intentions expressed in the speech. Therefore, this study also drew insights from Searle's classification of the five illocutionary acts, and Asiyanbola (2009)'s expounded illocutionary acts for this study in order for the illocutionary acts to effectively

capture the various actions performed by the teachers and students during classroom interactions in a more comprehensive way. These illocutionary acts are 8 in number, which are explained below:

- i.) **Expressive:** These are statements that express, convey, or communicate the ideas, knowledge, beliefs, thoughts, and feelings of the speaker to the hearer. This entails describing, informing, and explaining certain ideas and information to the listener
- ii.) **Interrogative:** These are statements that inquire or ask questions of the hearer. It is to inquire about some information from a listener.
- iii.) **Directive:** These are statements that give orders, commands, instructions, or directions from a speaker to a hearer.
- iv.) **Affirmative:** These are statements that consent, concur, or support the ideas or actions of a speaker by the hearer.
- v.) **Denial or Denying:** These are statements that oppose or reject the ideas or actions of a speaker by the hearer.
- vi.) **Vocative:** These are statements that pertain to addressing or calling names or appellation of an individual.
- vii.) **Corrective:** These are statements that amend, make, or set right an error performed by an individual
- viii.) **Commissive:** These are statements that entail making a commitment, like promising, vowing, threatening, or assuring a hearer by the speaker.

This study was concerned with analysing classroom interactions by using Asiyanbola's (2009) illocutionary acts mentioned above in order to find out the illocutionary acts employed in the classroom interactions between the teachers and the students.

3. Objectives of the study

The objective of this study is to examine the various illocutionary acts used in classroom interactions and assess the language of instruction used in senior secondary II (SS 2) science classrooms in selected secondary schools in Osun State.

3.1. Research questions

The paper intends to answer these research questions.

- i. What are the languages of instruction used in the science classrooms, and which one is mainly used?
- ii. What are the illocutionary acts used in the classroom interaction between the teachers and the students, and which illocutionary act is mainly used in classroom interaction?

4. Research methodology

The primary data were drawn from the analysis of classroom recordings from six classroom interactions of Senior Secondary School II (SS 2) science classes during Mathematics, Biology, and Physics classes. 6 secondary schools were randomly selected in six local government areas (L.G. As) of Osun State, which include Osogbo local government, Ede North local government, Ife East local government, Ife North local government, Ilesa West local government, and Ayedade local government. The researcher observed the six classroom interactions during Mathematics, Biology, or Physics classes, which were recorded and analysed using Speech Acts Theory by J.R. Searle, which was expounded by Asiyanbola (Asiyanbola, 2009).

5. Data analysis

In this section, the classroom interactions are analysed into two sections. The first section examines the languages in which the speech acts are used, which are categorised into three, namely the English speech acts, the Yoruba speech acts, and the bilingual speech acts. This is to find out the various languages used in the classrooms through these speech acts. The second section examines the various illocutionary acts used in classroom interaction. Some excerpts were drawn from the classroom interactions.

5.1. Languages of instruction used in the classroom interactions

From the classroom interactions, it is discovered that teachers make use of English, Yoruba and the bilingual language of instruction (code-mixing and code-switching English and Yoruba) in teaching of the students. Below are some excerpts that shows the use of these languages of instruction. In these excerpts, words in English are in normal interface, words in Yoruba are italicised and words in the bilingual language are italicised and boldened. The English translation of Yoruba statements and bilingual statements appear in superscript format. Some excerpts from the classroom interactions are seen below.

Excerpt 1

Student: Midpoint means ...

Teacher: *Sọ́ọ ní Yorubá. Kí ló tún mọ̀ sí?*

(Say it in Yoruba. What is the meaning?)

Student: *Midpoint ni aárín.* I mean the middle.

(Midpoint is middle)

Teacher: *Kí ni middle ní Yorubá?*

(What is middle in Yoruba?)

Student: *Aárín*

(Middle)

Teacher: *Aárín kí ni?*

(Middle of what?)

Student: *Aárín point*

(Middle point)

Teacher: *Kí se aárín lásán. Aárín méjì ni. Ibè ló ti pín sí méjì.* Now, point X is a midpoint of /AB/, point Y is a midpoint of /BC/ and point Z is a midpoint of what? (It is not middle alone. It is the midpoint. That is where it divided into two.)

Students: /CA/

Teacher: *Sé CA ni?*

(Is it CA?)

Students: Yes

Teacher: Okay, it is /CA/. That means this point is 4cm, 4cm will give us two 2cm. *Kíni èyí ma fún wa?* (What will this give us?)

Students: 3cm

Teacher: *Question wá ní find the side of the triangle XY. Kíni side X èyí ma jé?* (Our question is "Find the side of the triangle XY". What will side X be?)

Student: It is $\frac{2}{4}$

Teacher: Yes, we can consider it as parallelogram XZBC. *Èlòmí' maa kọ ti ẹ̀ ní XCYZ because the orientation is either clockwise or anticlockwise.* So, $\angle XZ = \angle BY = 3\frac{1}{2}$ cm, $\angle BX = \angle YZ = 2$ cm, $\angle XY = \angle ZC = 4$ cm. Let us find XY respectively. *Respectively means ní ń síse'n tẹ́lé.* Solve it. (Some will write theirs as XCYZ.)

Student: The answer is 6 and 4.

Teacher: That is correct. When you are given questions, try to translate it to your mother tongue. *Túmọ̀ ẹ̀rẹ̀ ní Yorubá.* Then the question is half solved. *Sé o gbọ̀ nńkan tí mo sọ? Side tó kéré over the longest side. Tí wọn bá ní kí a vote pé èdè wo ní ká maa ló ní ilé-ìwé,* I will prefer Yoruba to English. This is because it will boost your understanding. Do you understand? (Translate it in Yoruba. Did you hear what I said? The short side over the longest side. If they say we should vote for the language to be used in the school, I will prefer Yoruba to English.)

Students: Yes uncle

Teacher: In your mid-term exam, I may decide to bring everything I have been saying now and some of you will still score zero. *Now, báwo ní ènìyàn ọ̀ se ní mú adá bí kó bé ọmọ yẹn lórí dānu.* *Eloímí' nínú yín, a ti mọ̀ pé babá àti ìyá ẹ̀ jé, Babá ti lọ̀ sóko lọ̀ síse, ìyá náà ti lọ̀, wọn sí fí ọúnje sílẹ̀ nílẹ̀.* *Èní tó bá ń gbé pẹ̀lu parent ẹ̀ nínú yín, à fí tí parent ẹ̀ bá jé aláasẹ̀dānu ló kú tí kò ní mójútó owó tí ó ń san ní kò ní mọ̀ bóyá you are doing your assignment or not.* Let us look at another question: (Now, why won't someone take cutlass as if he/she should cut the child's neck. Some of you, we know that you are parenting yourself. Your fathers have gone to farm to work, likewise your mothers and they left food for you. For those of you living with your parents, unless the parents are wasters of resources is the situation whereby, they won't monitor you to know if you are doing your assignment or not.)

Students: Okay uncle

(Mathematics Class)

Excerpt 2

Teacher: Good morning. Last class we talked about the animals that use their lungs for gaseous exchange. Oyebode, mention one of them.

Student: Ostrich

Teacher: *O ti ń ro nú pé ju.* Bolarinwa, give us another example. (You are thinking for too long)

Student: Birds

Teacher: *Wá sọ pe apes.* Apes are generally birds. Can anyone give us examples of birds? (You will say apes)

Student: Duck

Student: Some people use to call monkey ape, is it correct?

Teacher: Ape is different of aves. *Àwọn ẹyẹ̀ ní aves. Ape ní àwọn ìnakí, ọ̀bọ.* Do you understand now? (Birds are aves. Apes are gorilla, monkey.)

Students: Yes

Teacher: Blessing, what's your question?

Student: *Sir, what is the meaning of ìnakí?* (Sir, what is the meaning of Inaki?)

Teacher: Gorilla

Teacher: Let us assume that this is the size of your lungs then, now that you are as big as this, if your size of lungs is small as this, the capacity of this lung will not be able to carry out the gaseous exchange you are exhibiting now. The internal organ also grow as you grow. Do you understand?

Students: Yes

Teacher: *Fún aṣẹ̀rẹ̀, nígbà tí o wà ní kẹ́kẹ́rẹ̀, orí ẹ̀ kò tóbi bá yí. Ká sọ pé nígbàí o wá tóbi bá yí, bí orí ẹ̀ se kéré nígbà yẹn, béèni brain ẹ̀ kéré.* *Now that you are an adult now, tí orí ẹ̀ ti tóbi, the space in your skull as in egungun tó wá lórí ẹ̀ ní wón pè ní skull yẹn. Space tó wá nínú ẹ̀ nígbàí o wà ní kẹ́kẹ́rẹ̀, size ẹ̀ ní brain nígbà yẹn, now tí o ti tóbi, ká sọ pé brain ẹ̀ kò dàgbà pẹ̀lu orí ẹ̀, ó rí pé brain ẹ̀ á ma mí logbologbo nínú orí ẹ̀.* So, as you grow, your internal organs also grow like liver, kidney etc. Is that understood? (For example, when you were small, your head was not as big as this. Let's say when you are big as this, as your head was small that time, that's how your brain is small. Now that you are an adult now, and now your head is big, the space in your skull as in the bone in your brain is what is called skull. The space that was in it when you were small was the size of your brain, now that you are big, assuming if you brain is not growing up with your head, you will see that your brain will be shaking inside your head.)

Students: Yes

(Biology Class)

Excerpt 3

Teacher: For us to get SC, let us first of all write what we are given. *We are given C which is 5 Mf abí?* (We are given C which is 5 Mf, isn't it?)

Students: Yes

Teacher: What is 5 Mf?

Students: $5/10 f$

Teacher: What else are we given?

Students: We are given V which is 330 V

Teacher: What else are we given?

Students: The frequency which is 500 H

Teacher: The question is already solved. From $SC = \frac{1}{2} \pi LC$ *we can get our LC abi?* (We can get our LC, isn't it?)

Students: Yes

Teacher: It is as simple as that. That will be equal to $\frac{1}{2} \pi \times f$ *You can solve it from this stage abi?* Calculate it and give me the answer. (You can solve it from this stage, isn't it?)

Students: 636.6β

Teacher: Are you getting it?

Students: Yes

Teacher: If that is the case should I give you a classwork? Find SC and π of an AC circuit of 230 V connected to a capacitor of 8 Mf.

Student: Okay uncle

Teacher: *Seun, you have finished abi?* (Seun, you have finished, isn't it?)

Student: No sir

Teacher: This topic is very applicable especially in companies where power transmission is very important. Who can tell me the number one place where they will need it?

Student: Power Holding Corporation of Nigeria (PHCN)

Teacher: Who can give me four major places where alternating current can be applied? *Óyá now.* (Answer me now)

Student: Telecommunications industry, Power stations, siting of radio stations, mechanical industry and in the field of medicine.

Teacher: Let's give him a round of applause. *Óyá, who can tell me what an alternating current is?* (Now, who can tell me what an alternating current is?)

Student: An alternating current is a current that is not direct but angulating.

(Physics Class)

Excerpt 4

Teacher: So, this is what you are asked to do. For A, I told you that when you are asked to find the union (U), it means the combination of the subsets of A and B. *Gbogbo nñkan tó wà nínu A pèlú gbogbo nñkan tó wà nínu B ni A U B.* Paul, tell me what is going to be A U B. (Everything that is in A and everything in B is A U B.)

Student: The answer is l, i, o, n, t, d, e and r.

Teacher: That is combination of the subsets of A and B. For question two, $A \cap B$ is what? *Moses, óyá tell us what A ∩ B is.* (Moses, now, tell us what A ∩ B is.)

Student: I don't know it ma.

Teacher: Rehoboth, what is $A \cap B$?

Student: It is i

Teacher: Is it only i?

Students: Yes

Teacher: That means i is $A \cap B$. *That is nñkan tó common láàrín A àì B.* Is it clear now? (That is what is common between A and B.)

Students: Yes

Teacher: This means that are men but not clerical staff. Women will be at the intersection. Out of this 52, men that are clerical staff will be here. *Àwọn tó ma wà láàrín méjì ní àwọn tó share information about men, clerical staff and women.* Do you get that? (Those that will be in between the two are those that share information about men, clerical staff and women.)

Students: Yes

Teacher: Clerical staff include both men and woman. The number of clerical staff is 38, the number of men is 52 and the total number is 79. Therefore, we have some men that are not clerical staff at all which is what we want to find. That means we have $52 - x$ where x is the number of men that are not clerical staff. *The universal set is 79 abi?* (The universal set is 79, isn't it?)

Students: Yes

Teacher: That is equal to $52 - x + x + 38 - x$, $79 = 52 + 38 - x$, $79 - 90 = -x$, $x = 11$. If the number of people that are in the intersection is 11, that means the number of men that are also clerical staff are 11. So, we have $52 - 11 = 41$. That means 41 men are not clerical staff. If our x is 11, what is $38 - 11$?

Students: 27

Teacher: The number of all women are 27 plus the number of all men that are clerical staff. Let x be the number of men that are clerical staff and we have got our x to be 11. *Therefore, we are going to remove the number 11 from 52 since gbogbo àwọn òkùnrin tó wà ní company yẹn ni 52. Àwọn tó jẹ clerical staff nínu wọn ni x.* Do we get it? (Therefore, we are going to remove the number 11 from 52 since all the males that are in the company are 52. Those that are clerical staff among them are x.)

Students: Yes

Teacher: *Àwọn yẹn ló wà ní middle tó jẹ intersection that is àwọn yẹn ló jẹ òkùnrin àì clerical staff. Normally, àwọn obìnrin ní ó jẹ clerical staff, but few of them are men.* So, they are among men but still clerical staff. So, after getting this intersection, we will minus it from 52. That is what give us 41 which is the number of men that are not clerical staff. *So, we have x as 11, $38 - 11$ ni àwọn tó jẹ both men and clerical staff. Ó ma fún wa ní 27 which is the number of*

women in the company while 27 + 11 will give us 38. 11 yen ni number of men that are clerical staff, àwọn tí kò se clerical staff ni 41. Tí abá roò papọ̀, ó fún wa ní 52. 52 yen ni total number of men. Then 27 + 11 ló ma fún wa ni total number of clerical staff. Is it clear?

(Those ones are at the middle that are intersection, that is, those are males and clerical staff. Normally, females are clerical staff but few of them are men. So, we have x as 11, 38-11 are those that are both men and clerical staff. It will give us 27 which is the number of women in the company while 27+11 will give us 38. That 11 is the number of men that are clerical staff, those that are not clerical staff are 41. If we add them together, it will give us 52. That 52 is the total number of men. Then, 27+11 will give us the total number of clerical staff.)

Students: Yes

Teacher: *Sé ó ti yé wa?* (Do we understand?)

Students: *Ó yé wa ma* (We understand ma.)

Teacher: *So, nnkan tí wọn ní ká wá ni number of men who are clerical staff which is what?* (So, what we are asked to find is the number of men who are clerical staff which is what?)

Students: 11

Teacher: So, 11 men are clerical staff. *Question tí wọn fún wa náa ni a máa interpret.* But there are some questions you may misinterpret if you are not careful. (It is the question we are given that we will interpret.)

Student: Is there no stable formula for the Venn diagram?

Teacher: There is no stable formula for it. The only thing is that you should interpret whatever information you are given and represent it by a circle. Do you understand?

Students: Yes ma

Teacher: *Wọn sọ pé ní company yen, gbogbo wọn jé 79. Now, gbogbo àwọn tó jé clerical staff je 38. Nínu gbogbo clerical staff, gbogbo obìnrin wà níbẹ̀. Ó mean pé 38 yí wà nínu ibí yí, ótún wà nínu ibí náa. So, tí àwọn okunrin tó jé clerical staff wà níbí yí, there is combination between men and clerical staff. Aye ti awon okunrin mu ninu clerical staff yen ni a represent with x. Se e understand?* (It says that in the company, they are all 79. Now, all the clerical staff are 38. Among the clerical staff, there are females there. It means that 38 will be here and also here. So, if the males who are clerical staff are here, there is combination between men and clerical staff. The space that contains males among the clerical staff is what we represent with x. Do you understand?)

Students: Yes

Teacher: *Now, ní ibí bayí, ó mean pé ta bá ti yọ àwọn okunrin tó jé clerical staff tán, àwọn obìnrin tó jé clerical staff ló ku.* That is 38 – x. *Ohun ni àwọn obìnrin yen. Now, wọn ní gbogbo men jé 52. Má gbàgbé pé ara number àwọn men yen ti lọ sí clerical staff. So, number àwọn men tó jé clerical staff jé 52 – x. Sé ó ti yé yin béyẹn?* (Now, in this place, it means that if we remove males that are clerical staff, the females that are clerical staff will remain. Those are the females. Now, they say all men that are clerical staff are 42-x. Do you understand like that?)

Students: *Ó yé wa ma.* (We understand ma.)

Teacher: So, that is what we have done. *Sé ó ti yé yin béyẹn?* (Do you understand like that?)

Students: *Ó yé wa ma.* (We understand ma.)

Teacher: So, we now said that the universal set is equal to all these. We then got 11. Is that clear?

Students: Yes

Teacher: If we subtract 11 from 52, ó ma fún wa ní 41. *So, the number of men tó jé pé company yen ló wà but wọn kī se clerical staff ni 41. Then 38 – 11 ló fún wa ní 27 which is the total number of women who are clerical staff. So, what is the number of men that are clerical staff only?* (So, the number of men who are in the company but not clerical staff is 41. Then, 38-11 gives us 27 which is the total number of women who are clerical staff.)

Students: 27

Teacher: So, the number of men that are men that are clerical staff is 27. *Sé ó ti yé yin béyẹn?* (Do you understand ma?)

Students: Yes ma

(Mathematics Class)

5.2. Summary of findings on the language of instruction used in classroom interactions

As seen in the above excerpts, three languages of instruction are used in the classroom interactions. These include English, Yoruba, and the bilingual language (code-mixing or code-switching of both English and Yoruba). There are many instances where the teachers make use of English speech acts, for instance, the teachers use English to teach in the classroom. Sometimes, the teachers make use of Yoruba speech acts in which Yoruba is used to explain some concepts, and also, the teachers make use of bilingual language, which is the code-mixing or code-switching of both English and Yoruba languages together.

Table 1: Number of English speech acts, Yoruba speech acts, and Bilingual speech acts used in the classroom interactions

Class Interaction	English speech act	Yoruba speech act	Bilingual speech act	Total
Class Interaction I	144	-	-	144
Class Interaction II	190	18	21	229
Class Interaction III	150	16	52	218
Class Interaction IV	182	-	10	192
Class Interaction V	144	5	34	183
Class Interaction VI	166	-	7	173
TOTAL	976	39	124	1139

From the analysis of the classroom recording, out of 1139 speech acts used in the six classroom interactions analysed, 976 English speech acts are used, 39 Yoruba speech acts are used, and 124 bilingual speech acts are used. Therefore, the English speech acts are mainly used in all the 6 classroom interactions, while the bilingual speech act, which involved codemixing English and Yoruba, was the second speech act used in the 6 classroom interactions. This implied that the English language is still the major language used in classroom interactions, but sometimes, English is complemented with Yoruba during classroom interactions in order to help students have a deeper and clearer understanding of the topic the teacher is teaching.

5.3. Illocutionary acts in the classroom discourse

The eight (8) illocutionary acts are used in classroom interactions. Some excerpts are drawn from the classroom interactions, which are seen below.

1. Expressives: There are statements that are expressive in the class interactions to convey and express information to the students which entails explaining, describing, and informing the students about the topic under consideration. The expressive are italicised and boldened in the excerpts showing this illocutionary act below.

Excerpt 1

Teacher: *Last class we met, we started with transport system in man and I said for the transport system to be made possible in man, there are three features that are necessary. I said we have blood which is the circulating fluid that helps to carry materials from one part of the body to another part of the body. I said we have the lymph which is also a medium for circulating materials in higher animals like you.*

(Biology Class)

These statements above are English speech acts which are expressive. The statements are expressive because it describes the transport system in man.

Excerpt 2

Teacher: *I said we have blood vessels which are of three types. We have the arteries, veins and capillaries. I said blood vessels are channels through which blood flows. Blood do not move anyhow within the body because it possess a close circulatory system. I also said the third feature is the heart which is the pumping organ that pumps blood as it beats. The heart is able to do this because it is a muscular organ which has the ability of contracting and relapsing. This is why it has been able to beat since the day you were given birth to and it will continue to beat throughout lifetime.*

(Biology Class)

These statements above are English speech acts which are expressive. The statements are expressive because they describe the blood vessels and the heart.

Excerpt 3

Teacher: *Phagocytes help in preventing diseases. Whenever, you have bacteria and virus, the phagocytes break it down and help the body to prevent diseases. That is why white blood cells are soldiers of the body. Not only that, they produce antibodies that helps to neutralize the effect of poison in the body.*

(Biology Class)

These statements above include English speech acts which are expressive because the teacher is describing the functions of the white blood cell.

Excerpt 4

Teacher: *From the diagram, we can see that the line XY is the longest among them. Oun ló gùn jù. Mathematics is the easiest subject.*

(Oun ló gùn jù means "It is the longest")

(Mathematics Class)

These statements above contain 2 English speech acts and 1 Yoruba speech act which are expressive since the teacher is explaining the steps to solve the question to the students.

Excerpt 5

Teacher: *So, we are to find /XY/ and /CY/. So, we must write our orientation. /AX//AC = /XY//AB/ = /XY//BC/. This is our orientation and once you get the orientation, it is simple. AC /AY= AY +YC, AY/AC=2x/6. Over 8 mà ló ye kó jé. AX/AB will be 8AY= 10, AY=10/8, AY=1¹/₄ cm. Therefore, CY will be*

5- 1¹/₄. What will it remain?

(Over 8 mà ló ye kó jé means "It supposed to be over 8")

Students: 3¹/₄ cm

(Mathematics Class)

The statements above contain English speech acts and a bilingual speech act (codemixing English and Yoruba). The statements that are italicised and bolded by the teacher are expressive because the teacher is explaining the steps to solve the question. Also, the students' response is also expressive since they are saying the answer to the question asked by the teacher.

Excerpt 6

Teacher: *Question wá ní find the side of the triangle XY.* Kíni side X èyí ma jé?

(Our question is "Find the side of the triangle XY. What will side X be?")

Student: It is $\frac{2}{4}$

(Mathematics Class)

These statements above contain 2 bilingual speech acts (code-mixing English and Yoruba) and 1 English speech act. The italicised and boldened statement of the teacher is an expressive whereby the teacher is stating the question that is to be solved. Also, the student's response is expressive because the student is asserting the answer to the question asked by the teacher.

Excerpt 6

Teacher: When we have a resistor here and a resistor here, the amount of the work that will be done here is different form the amount of work that will be done here. The only reason why they can have the same voltage is if they have different current. Now, the same thing is applicable when we have the one of capacitor connected in series in the alternating current. Now, in an alternating current, you will not have $V = IR$ as we had it in resistor connection.

(Physics Class)

These statements above contain English speech acts and they are expressives used by the teacher to explain the topic about current to the students.

2. Interrogatives: There are statements which are interrogatives in the class interactions which the teachers used to ask the students questions. Some excerpts are seen below in which the interrogatives are italicised and boldened

Excerpt 1

Teacher: Be careful, three of you at the back. *What are you discussing?*

(Biology Class)

These statements are English speech acts in which the second statement is an interrogative that the teacher used to question the three students discussing at the back of the classroom.

Excerpt 2

Teacher: Yesterday, I talked about blood and I said blood is a tissue and I told you the reason why blood is a tissue. *So, can anybody tell me why blood is a tissue?*

Student: Blood is a tissue because it is a combination of different cells.

(Biology Class)

In the above excerpt, there are English speech acts whereby the italicised and boldened statement is an interrogative because the teacher is asking the student a question.

Excerpt 3

Teacher: *Another name for the red blood cells is what?*

Students: Erythrocyte

(Biology Class)

These statements above are English speech acts which are interrogative and expressive. The first statement above is an interrogative because the teacher is asking the students a question about red blood cells.

Excerpt 4

Teacher: Adeleke, midpoint of AB, BC and AC, *Kí ló tún mò sí?*

(Kí ló tún mò sí? means "What does it mean?")

(Mathematics Class)

In the above excerpt, there is a bilingual speech act (code-switching from English to Yoruba) which is an interrogative which is asking one of the students a question.

Excerpt 5

Teacher: *Now, point X is a midpoint of /AB/, point Y is a midpoint of /BC/ and point Z is a midpoint of what?*

Students: /CA/

(Mathematics Class)

The excerpt above contains English speech acts in which the italicised and boldened statement from the teacher is an interrogative whereby the teacher is asking the students a question.

Excerpt 6

Teacher: *Oyegbemi, kí ní ìtumọ̀ midpoint?* (What is the meaning of midpoint?)

Student: Middle

Teacher: *Kí ní a máa n pè' é ní Yorubá?* (What is it called in Yoruba?)

Student: A'árín (Middle)

(Mathematics Class)

In the above excerpt, there is a bilingual speech act, a English speech act and Yoruba speech acts. The italicised and boldened statements from the teacher are interrogative in order to ask a student a question.

Excerpt 7

Teacher: What is 5 Mf?

Students: $\frac{5}{10}$ f
(Physics Class)

These statements above are English speech acts which are interrogative and expressive. The first statement above is an interrogative because the teacher is asking the students a question about the value of M_f .

3. Directives: There are statements that are directives, the class interactions that the teachers use to instruct, direct or command the students. Some excerpts are shown below in which the directives are italicised and boldened.

Excerpt 1

Teacher: *Two of you stand up! Stand up!* I am teaching, you are fighting over bags.
(Biology Class)

In the above excerpt, there are English speech acts in which the statements italicised and boldened are directive. The first and second statements are directive because the teacher is ordering the students to stand up.

Excerpt 2

Teacher: *I want you to read your notes when you get home.* I move on to white blood cell and after explaining the white blood cell, you will tell me the differences between the red blood cell and the white blood cell. **So, you have to listen attentively.**
(Biology Class)

The above statements are English speech acts whereby the italicised and boldened statements are directives. The first statement is directive because the teacher is instructing the students to read their notes and the third statement is also directive because the teacher is ordering the student to listen attentively.

Excerpt 3

Teacher: Why is it swollen? *That is an assignment for you.* Now I have an official assignment for you. In a tabular form, differentiate between white blood cell and red blood cell. **Submit tomorrow morning before the assembly.**
(Biology Class)

The statements above are English speech acts in which the italicised and boldened statements are directive. The second statement is directive because the giving the students an assignment and the fifth statement is a directive because the teacher is ordering the students to submit their assignment the next day.

Excerpt 4

Teacher: The assignment I gave you yesterday, some of you wrote the wrong orientation. **Let us solve the questions.**
(Mathematics Class)

In the above excerpt, English speech acts are contained in which the statement italicised and boldened is a directive which the teacher used to give the students instruction on the questions to solve.

Excerpt 5

Teacher: *When you get home, you should do it yourself and avoid cultivating the habit of copying your friends.*
(Mathematics Class)

An English speech act is contained in the excerpt above which is a directive since the teacher is giving the students instruction on what to do at home.

Excerpt 6

Teacher: So, $\frac{XZ}{BY} = 3\frac{1}{2}$ cm, $\frac{BX}{YZ} = 2$ cm, $\frac{XY}{ZC} = 4$ cm. **Let us find XY respectively.** Respectively means ní n sísè n tɛ̀lé. **Solve it.**
(Mathematics Class)

The excerpt above are English speech acts and a bilingual speech act in which the italicised and boldened statements are directive. The second and fourth statements are directive because the teacher is ordering the students to solve a particular question.

Excerpt 7

Teacher: If that is the case, should I give you a classwork? **Find SC and π of an AC circuit of 230 V connected to a capacitor of 8 Mf.**
(Physics Class)

These statements above consist of English speech acts which are interrogative and directive. The second statement is directive because the teacher is ordering the students to solve a question.

4. Affirmatives: These are statements which are affirmative in the class interactions which the teachers used to accept, support and agree with the ideas of the students and vice versa. Some excerpts are shown below in which the directives are italicised and emboldened.

Excerpt 1

Teacher: I said we are going to look at these features one after the other. Isn't it?
Students: Yes
(Biology Class)

These statements above are English speech acts. The response of the students is an affirmative because the students are consenting to the question of the teacher.

Excerpt 2

Student: Blood is a tissue because it is a combination of different cells.

Teacher: *That is correct.*

(Biology Class)

These statements above are English speech acts. The response of the teacher is affirmative because it affirms the teachers' view about the answer the student gave.

Excerpt 3

Teacher: Sé CA ni?

Students: *Yes*

Teacher: *Okay, it is /CA/.* That means this point is 4cm, 4cm will give us two 2cm.

(Mathematics Class)

In the excerpt above, there is a bilingual speech act and English speech acts. The italicised statements are affirmative. The students' response is affirmative because the students are affirming their confidence that the answer they gave the teacher is correct. The teacher's response is also affirmative because the teacher is supporting that the answer given by the students are correct.

Excerpt 5

Teacher: $CD/12 = 16/24$, $3CD = 24$, $CD = 24/3$, $CD = 8$ cm. I hope it is clear?

Students: *Yes*

(Mathematics Class)

The excerpt above contains English speech acts. The students' response is an affirmative since the students are confirming that they understand to what the teacher is saying.

Excerpt 6

Teacher: We are to find /BE/. If this line and this line are parallel, it means both angles are the same. What is the corresponding angle?

Students: AB

Teacher: *Yes, I am listening.*

(Mathematics Class)

In the excerpt above, there are English speech acts in which the italicised statement is an affirmative because the teacher is affirming that he is listening to what the student is saying.

Excerpt 7

Teacher: How many of you have seen a mast before?

Students: *Yes, we have seen it before.*

(Physics Class)

These statements above are English speech acts which include an interrogative and affirmative. The second statement is an affirmative by the students to respond positively to the question that they have seen a mast before.

5. Denial: There are statements that oppose or reject the ideas or action of a teacher by the students and vice versa. Some excerpts are shown below in which the denial is italicised and boldened

Excerpt 1

Teacher: So, any question on red blood cell?

Students: *No*

(Biology Class)

English speech acts can be seen above. After the teacher asked a question from the students, there was a denial because the students expressed that they have no question as regards red blood cell to the teacher.

Excerpt 2

Teacher: Ewo ló tún kù?

(What is remaining?)

Student: EF

Teacher: *No, it is not EF.*

(Mathematics Class)

In the excerpt above, a Yoruba speech act and English speech act are seen. After the teacher asked the students a question and the students responded by stating the answer to the question asked by the teacher, there is a denial because the teacher expressed his opposition to the answer given by the students.

Excerpt 3

Teacher: Do we have AB?

Students: *No*

(Mathematics Class)

There are English speech acts in the above excerpts. After the teacher asked the students a question, there is a denial because the students are expressing opposition to the question the teacher asked.

Excerpt 4

Teacher: By this virtue of our diagram, BE= CD is a parallelogram, BC=ED is a parallelogram. If BE= CD and my BC=ED. Is there any problem there?

Student: *No*

(Mathematics Class)

These statements above contain English speech acts. After the teacher asked the students a question, the students use denial to express that there is no problem as regards what the teacher is explaining.

Excerpt 5

Teacher: How are we going to get our SC? $SC = \frac{1}{2} \pi LC$. Your SC is the capacity reactant while your C is the capacitor. Did you get it now?

Students: *No, we have not gotten it.*

(Physics Class)

These statements above are English speech acts. After the teacher asked the students if they are comprehending what he is explaining, the students' response is a denial because the students are expressing that they do not understand what the teacher has just explained to them.

6. Vocative: There are statements that pertain to addressing or calling of names or appellation of the students or the teachers in the classroom interactions. Some excerpts which show vocatives are italicised and boldened below.

Excerpt 1

Teacher: I said an adult man have 4.5 litres of blood.

Student: *Aunty*, it is 5.6 litres

(Biology Class)

These statements above are English speech acts. In the second statement, a vocative is used by the student to call the appellation of the teacher so as to draw her attention to the correct answer.

Excerpt 2

Teacher: *Ola*, say something about the red blood cell?

Student: It is small, round and has depression in it.

Teacher: *Class monitress*, say something about the abundance of red blood cell?

Student: We have 5 million red blood cells in a pinch of blood.

(Biology Class)

English speech acts are contained in the above excerpts. There are vocatives used by the teacher to call the name of a student and the appellation of another student.

Excerpt 3

Teacher: This means $\frac{3}{6} = 2 \times ZY$. $\frac{1}{2} = \frac{2}{XY}$. Cross multiply implies that $ZY = 2 \times 2$ cm which is equal 4cm. These are the things you need to master. I don't think I made these difficult for you. This is what geometric ratio is and it has a particular orientation. Let us move on so that we can do one or two things. It is very simple but you have to practice it. Is that okay?

Students: Yes *uncle*

(Mathematics Class)

The above excerpt contains the English speech acts. From the response of the students, there is a vocative used by the students to call the teacher.

Excerpt 4

Teacher: Let us look at another question.

Students: Okay *uncle*

(Mathematics Class)

English speech acts are used in the excerpt which contains the vocative used by the students in calling the teacher's name after expressing their agreement to what the teacher is saying.

Excerpt 5

Teacher: Some of you wrote rubbish. *Mayowa*, I will beat you because you wrote the wrong orientation.

(Mathematics Class)

In the above excerpt, English speech acts are used. In the second statement, the teacher made use of vocative to call the name of a student who made a mistake in his assignment.

Excerpt 6

Teacher: I also said that there are three forms of resistance as far as AC circuit is concerned. I need three people to tell me one after the other. *Segun*, give me one of them.

Student: Inductor

Teacher: *Soji*, another one?

Student: Resistor

Teacher: *Jane*, another one?

Student: Capacitor

(Physics Class)

These above statements are English speech acts. The teacher made use of vocatives to call the names of students that should answer the questions.

7. Corrective: There are statements that amend, makes or set right an error performed by a teacher or student. Below are some excerpts showing the correctives which are italicised below.

Excerpt 1

Teacher: So, as I was saying, blood is a tissue because it consists of different cells coming together to perform a particular function. It is a tissue in a fluid or liquid form and I said another form and I said an adult man have 4.5 litres of blood.

Student: Aunty, *it is 5.6 litres*

(Classroom Interaction 1: Biology)

These statements above contain English speech acts. From the student's response, corrective is used to correct or amend the teacher's mistake.

Excerpt 2

Teacher: Korede, so tiẹ. (Korede, say your own)

Student: When we are breathing in, we breathe through the lungs, the ribs and stallum move upwards and outwards and the diaphragm will contract.

Teacher: *Korede aṣi abúro`rẹ̀ ọ̀se dáadáa, wón ti gbàgbé.*

(Korede and his younger one did not do well, they have forgotten.)

(Biology Class)

In the above excerpt, there are statement with Yoruba speech acts and English speech act. After the teacher called the student to answer a question and the student gave the answer, the teacher's response is corrective. This is to correct the students that they didn't answer the question accurately and correctly.

8. Commissive: There are statements that entail making commitment like promising, vowing, threatening or assuring a student by the teacher or vice versa. Some excerpts showing commissive italicised and boldened below.

Excerpt 1

Student: When the blood leaves the heart to the arteries to other parts of the body, is the blood oxygenated or deoxygenated blood?

Teacher: It is deoxygenated blood. *We will meet in the next class.*

(Biology Class)

These statements above are English speech acts. There is a commissive in the second statement made by the teacher because the teacher is promising the students that the next class will hold.

Excerpt 2

Teacher: Some of you wrote rubbish. Mayowa, I *will beat you because you wrote the wrong orientation.*

(Mathematics Class)

These statements above contain English speech acts. In the second statement, there is a commissive because the teacher is vowing that he will beat a student that did the wrong thing in the assignment.

Excerpt 3

Teacher: *In your mid-term exam, I may decide to bring everything I have been saying now and some of you will still score zero.*

(Mathematics Class)

The excerpt above has English speech acts in which there is a commissive because the teacher is saying he may probably bring out some questions in the examination which is a kind of promise.

Excerpt 4

Teacher: Do this homework. *We will meet next class.* Good day class.

(Mathematics Class)

These statements above contain English speech acts. The second statement is a commissive because the teacher is guaranteeing the students that he will come to the next class.

Excerpt 5

Teacher: *So, they are going to give you your capacitor value in Micro farad (Mf).*

(Physics Class)

The excerpt above has an English speech act which is. This is because the teacher is assuring the students that they will be given their capacitor value in Micro farad.

5.4. Summary of findings on the language of instruction used in the classroom interactions

From the analysis of the class interactions, the eight illocutionary acts are used during the six classroom interactions, including expressive, directive, interrogative, affirmative, denial, vocative, corrective, and commissive. Out of the 1139 illocutionary acts used in the six classroom interactions analysed, 588 statements are expressive, 272 statements are interrogative, 64 statements are directive, 109 statements are affirmative, 28 statements are denying, 61 statements are vocative, 3 statements are corrective, and 14 statements are commissive as seen in the table below.

Table 2: Number of Illocutionary acts used in the classroom interactions

Class Interaction	EXP	INT	DIR	AFF	DEN	VOC	COR	COM	Total
Class Interaction I	79	38	9	7	1	8	1	1	144
Class Interaction II	111	60	13	26	10	4	-	5	229
Class Interaction III	118	42	10	20	4	21	2	1	218
Class Interaction IV	95	43	13	23	4	11	-	3	192
Class Interaction V	88	39	14	21	7	12	-	2	183
Class Interaction VI	97	50	5	12	2	5	-	2	173
TOTAL	588	272	64	109	28	61	3	14	1139

N.B: EXP represents Expressive; INT represents Interrogative; DIR represents Directive; AFF represents Affirmative; DEN represents Denial; COR represents Corrective and COM represents Commissive.

From the analysis, the main illocutionary act used in the six classroom interactions is expressive. This is because the main action teachers perform in the classroom is to express, convey, and communicate knowledge and ideas to the students, which involves describing, informing, and explaining to the students. The second main illocutionary act used in the six classroom interactions is interrogative. This is because, aside from teachers explaining to the students, they also perform the action of asking the students questions in order to know if the students are really getting the ideas being conveyed. All these illocutionary acts are used to ensure the effective conveyance of information by the teachers to the students about the different topics in Mathematics, Biology, and Physics. Also, the use of Yoruba to complement English at different points in the classroom interactions enhances a deeper understanding of the difficult concepts in these subjects by the students. This is consistent with Oso's (2024b) assertion that bilingual language of instruction is the best way to teach at the secondary school level since it improves students' comprehension and performance in science courses. Therefore, using the students' mother tongue knowledge to enhance their English language proficiency does not undermine English's position as the primary language of instruction in Nigeria, but rather strengthens it. (Oso, 2024b).

6. Conclusion

Classroom interactions are more than just a conversation, but an encompassing discourse that ensures that all intentions and aspirations of the teachers are made known to the students in an educationally rewarding way. Additionally, it is crucial to make sure that the language employed in these classroom discussions is suitable for properly conveying and interpreting all of the teacher's goals to the students in a way that they can comprehend (Olagbaju and Akinsowon, 2014). Even though English is still the primary language of instruction in Nigerian secondary schools, it is advised that it be supplemented with the child's mother tongue because doing so will improve students' comprehension and performance in their subjects in ESL classrooms.

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